

Enhancing Mechatronics Pedagogy: Integrating Gamified Storytelling Techniques in Robot Programming Instruction

Mika Letonsaari

*The Institute of Intelligent and Interactive
Technology*

University of Economics Ho Chi Minh City

Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7249-8632>

Abstract—As robotics and automation become more widespread, there is a growing need for methods that enable understanding of robot programming in less technical terms. This paper explores the use of gamified storytelling as a novel approach to mechatronics education, employing interactive stories created with Twine storytelling software. To demonstrate the feasibility of this approach, we developed an automatic translation system that converts Twine's Twee code into ABB RobotStudio's RAPID programming language. The effectiveness of this method is illustrated through the implementation of a Turnstile Machine and a Universal Turing Machine, highlighting its potential as a valuable educational tool in teaching complex robot programming concepts.

Keywords—robotics, education, RobotStudio, RAPID, Twine, gamification, storytelling

I. INTRODUCTION

As automation becomes increasingly pervasive across industries, robotics and mechatronics are no longer the exclusive domain of specialist engineers. Understanding the underlying logic and possible applications of these technologies is becoming crucial for a broader audience with non-technical backgrounds. Many solutions have been tried to overcome these obstacles [1][2]. Here I introduce a novel storytelling approach which can transform the learning experience by embedding technical content within interactive and relatable narratives. This approach not only facilitates the acquisition of programming skills for students but also offers a valuable tool for non-technical professionals, enabling them to better understand and interact with robotic systems.

This novel study builds upon my previous research, in which I demonstrated that gamified narratives structurally and functionally correspond to computer programming [3]. Branching stories, written in natural language, incorporate elements such as conditional branching and execution flow and can be used to train computational thinking skills. In another study, we explored the use of stories to control educational Arduino-based robots [4]. In this article, I extend this concept to more advanced engineering education. Twee formatted gamified stories created with Twine software are automatically translated into RAPID programming language enabling their use in controlling robots within the virtual ABB RobotStudio Suite or with actual industrial robots.

II. METHODS

A. Twine Storytelling Software

Twine (twinery.org) is an open source storytelling software widely used in game development and education. It

has an intuitive user interface and it has been used with children as young as ten years old [5]. The software allows the creation of nonlinear stories through paragraphs linked together, enabling complex narrative structures. Stories can be exported either as playable HTML files or in the native Twee format.

B. RAPID and ABB RobotStudio Suite

RobotStudio is a widely used simulation and offline programming software developed by ABB. The software provides a virtual environment for programming, simulating, and optimizing the operations of robots. RAPID is the programming language used in ABB RobotStudio. Complex robotic behaviors are created through sequences of instructions, loops, conditional statements, and routines. RAPID is a commonly used tool in education for teaching students the principles of robot programming.

C. Computational Models

In this study, I implement two robot logic programs as interactive stories. These stories are then automatically translated into RAPID code for use in RobotStudio. Robot logic does not always need to be complex; often, simple and more limited models of computation, such as finite-state machines (FSM), are sufficient. The first model is, therefore, a simple turnstile machine, which is easily modeled using an FSM. For a previous implementation of this model see Letonsaari and Selin (2017) [3]. Turing complete system is a computational model that can execute any algorithmically described program [6]. Most general purpose programming languages such as RAPID are Turing complete. The second robot logic program is a universal Turing machine implementation. There exists many universal Turing machines which differ by number of required states, symbols, and the instruction set. The classic implementation is by Minsky (1962) [7][8] which uses 7 states and 4 symbols. Optimized machines are provided by Rogozhin (1996) [9] and here we use his model with 4 states and 6 symbols.

III. RESULTS

Two interactive stories describing robot logic programs were implemented. The turnstile machine logic, in particular, is straightforward to implement (see Supplementary Materials). An interesting aspect is the exploration of various physical implementations of this machine. Beyond the typical gate mechanism, a robot can, for instance, control a beam gate typically found in parking lots or manage objects on a conveyor belt. Actions can be triggered, for example, by sensors or human interaction.

Fig. 1. Rogozhin's (4,6) Universal Turing machine implemented as an interactive Twine story.

Implementing the Universal Turing machine was a more complex modeling project. In Twine, stories are composed of paragraphs connected by links. Rogozhin's (4, 6) machine, which has 4 states and 6 symbols, was modeled in this framework. In addition to the start and end ('halt') paragraphs, four paragraphs were dedicated to describing the four machine states. For each state, six possible transitions were modeled, resulting in a total of 24 transition paragraphs. This brings the interactive story to a total of 30 paragraphs: 2 for the start and end, 4 for the states, and 24 for the transitions. The story structure is visually presented in Fig. 1.

A python script was created to automatically translate Twine twee code to RAPID programming language code. This is fairly straightforward as advanced scripting features were not used in Twine. However, for both Twine and RAPID code, application-specific rules must be established. This involves modeling the controls for specific robots within RobotStudio and determining how these features are accessed and manipulated from within Twine stories.

In this application, we utilized a compact 6-axis robot model, the ABB IRB 140, equipped with a Smart Gripper. The tape was modeled as a chain of small objects surrounding the robot. The robot, capable of rotating 360 degrees around its base, can traverse the simulated tape by

Fig. 2. ABB IRB 140 robot with six gray scale circles presenting symbol values from 0 to 5 and a line of objects representing the symbol tape.

turning left or right. The placement of objects, their distance from the robot, represent a symbol code ranging from 0 to 5. The setup is presented in Fig. 2.

IV. DISCUSSION

Gamified storytelling offers a novel approach that could serve as an accessible introduction to robotics, particularly for individuals from non-technical backgrounds and younger learners familiar with game technologies. This paper presents two case studies. While technical in nature, they demonstrate the potential of nonlinear stories for robot programming.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Computer code, example stories, and implementations related to this study are available at the GitHub repository: <https://github.com/mletonsa/Twee-to-RAPID>.

REFERENCES

- [1] G.F. Rossano, C. Martinez, M. Hedelind, S. Murphy, and T.A. Fuhlbrigge, 2013, August. "Easy robot programming concepts: An industrial perspective". In *2013 IEEE international conference on automation science and engineering (CASE)* (pp. 1119-1126). IEEE.
- [2] O. Heimann, and J. Guhl. "Industrial robot programming methods: A scoping review." In *2020 25th IEEE International Conference on Emerging Technologies and Factory Automation (ETFA)*, vol. 1, pp. 696-703. IEEE, 2020.
- [3] M. Letonsaari, and J. Selin. "Modeling computational algorithms using nonlinear storytelling methods of computer game design." *Procedia computer science* 119 (2017): 131-138.
- [4] M. Letonsaari, and J. Selin. "Nonlinear storytelling method for interdisciplinary and cross expertise-level communication of knowledge." In *International Conference on Interdisciplinarity of Knowledge, Education and Research, IKER 2019*. 2019.
- [5] K. M. Tran, 2016. "Her story was complex": A Twine workshop for ten- to twelve-year-old girls. *E-Learning and Digital Media*, 13(5-6), 212-226
- [6] A. Turing. "On computable numbers, with an application to the Entscheidungsproblem." *J. of Math* 58, no. 345-363 (1936): 5.
- [7] M.L. Minsky, "Size and structure of universal Turing machines using tag systems", *Recursive Function Theory, Proceedings of Symposia in Pure Mathematics, vol. V*, American Mathematical Society, Providence, R.I. 1962, pp. 229-238
- [8] Robinson, Raphael M. "Minsky's small universal Turing machine." *International Journal of Mathematics* 2.05 (1991): 551-562.
- [9] Rogozhin, Yurii. "Small universal Turing machines." *Theoretical Computer Science* 168, no. 2 (1996): 215-240.